

Oxidation of 4-chlorobenzyl alcohol by polymer supported chromic acid – Kinetic and mechanistic study

S. A. Kakade, A. S. Varale, V. Y. Sonawane and N. P. Hilage*

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-415 004, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : shital_kakade09@yahoo.com

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Abstract : The kinetics of oxidation of 4-chlorobenzyl alcohol with polymer supported chromic acid in 1 : 4 dioxane has been studied. The reaction is found to be zero order each in [alcohol] and [oxidant]. The effect of substituent on the rate of oxidation and the % of cross linking in polymeric resin (oxidant) are studied. Thermodynamic parameters are evaluated. The reaction product has been isolated and characterized by its derivative. A probable mechanism of oxidation is proposed.

Keywords : Kinetic, oxidation, polymer supported chromic acid, 4-chlorobenzyl alcohol, Ambersep 900 ($\bar{O}H$).

Introduction

Chromic acid is known to be a versatile oxidizing agent. The major use of chromic acid in synthetic chemistry is in the oxidation of primary and secondary alcohols to aldehydes and ketones respectively. During the oxidation of primary alcohols, the aldehydes formed are easily oxidized, and are converted to the corresponding carboxylic acid. The use of polymer supported chromic acid has some advantage in yield, purity of product, ease of separation and selective oxidation¹. The oxidation process ends at aldehyde only. Polymer bound reagents have been reported for the oxidation of various alcohols².

In this article we present oxidation of 4-chlorobenzyl alcohol by polymer supported chromic acid. Ambersep 900 ($\bar{O}H$), a strong anion exchange resin is supported with chromium(vi) oxide and used as an oxidant. In order to study the effect of cross linking on the rate of reaction a polystyrene supported chromium(vi) oxide was prepared from 4, 6 and 6.5% chloromethylated polystyrene.

Results

Effect of change in concentration of 4-chlorobenzyl alcohol on rate of reaction :

The kinetic study is carried out at different concentration of 4-chlorobenzyl alcohol (13.4×10^{-6} –

Fig. 1. Plot of optical density vs time.

33.6×10^{-6} kg) at constant concentration of solvent (5×10^{-3} dm³, 1 : 4 dioxane) and oxidant (140×10^{-6} kg) at 318 K. The plot (Fig. 1) of absorbance against time was linear in all runs and passing through origin. This shows that the reaction is zero order to concentration of 4-chlorobenzyl alcohol (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of change in concentration of 4-chlorobenzyl alcohol on rate of reaction

4-Chlorobenzyl alcohol $\times 10^{-6}$ (kg)	$k \times 10^{-6}$ (s ⁻¹)
13.4	6.66
20.2	6.86
27.0	6.94
33.6	6.66

Effect of change in concentration of oxidant on rate of reaction :

Studying the reaction at a different concentration

of oxidant (120×10^{-6} – 180×10^{-6} kg) and keeping constant concentration of 4-chlorobenzyl alcohol (120.2×10^{-6} kg) and solvent (5×10^{-3} dm³) at 318 K, zero order rate constant was found (Table 2).

Table 2. Effect of change in concentration of oxidant on rate of reaction

Oxidant $\times 10^{-6}$ (kg)	$k \times 10^{-6}$ (s ⁻¹)
120	6.88
140	6.86
160	6.98
180	6.90

Effect of dielectric constant on rate of reaction :

It was found that as the dielectric constant of medium increased, zero order rate constant was also increased this including $r^* < r$ (where r^* and r refer to the radii of activated complex and reactant species the respectively) at constant concentration of 4-chlorobenzyl alcohol (20.2×10^{-6} kg) and constant concentration of oxidant (140×10^{-6} kg), solvent (1 : 4 dioxane, 5×10^{-3} dm³) at 318 K as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Effect of dielectric constant on rate of reaction

Solvent 5×10^{-3} (dm ³)	Dielectric constants	$k \times 10^{-6}$ (s ⁻¹)
Cyclohexane	2.0	5.76
CCl ₄	2.2	6.40
1 : 4 Dioxane	2.2	6.86
Chloroform	4.8	10.78

Effect of % of cross linking on rate of reaction :

All those reactions which are catalyzed homogeneously by acid or base have also been carried out in the presence of cationic and anionic ion exchange resins³. The structural factors of resin such as effect of pore and particle size, solvent, crosslink density, adsorption, diffusion and distribution phenomenon are found to vary from resin to resin. While studying the effect of % of cross linking on the rate of reaction, a variation in rate of reaction was observed.

The effect of % of cross linking in the polymeric resin (oxidant) was studied between 4, 6 and 6.5% (cross linked with DVB). It was found that zero order

rate constant increases as the % of cross linking in polymeric resin decreases⁴. The observation indicates that the reaction is diffusion controlled because the acid sites in the resin are less accessible and more highly cross linked. Due to increased cross linked density, there is steric interference at the catalytic site⁵ (Table 4) (Fig. 2).

Table 4. Effect of % of cross linking on rate of reaction

% of cross linking	$k \times 10^{-6}$ (s ⁻¹)
4	8.33
6	6.86
6.5	6.41

Fig. 2. Effect of cross linking on the rate of reaction.

Effect of temperature on the rate of reaction :

The reaction was carried out at temperature ranging between 313–328 K at constant concentration of 4-chlorobenzyl alcohol (20.2×10^{-6} kg) and at constant concentration of solvent (5×10^{-3} dm³, 1 : 4 dioxane). It is found that zero order rate constant depends on the reaction temperature (shown in (Table 5) (Fig. 3)). The values of enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger), entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger), free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger), energy of activation (E_a), frequency factor (A) and temperature coefficient were calculated (Table 6).

Discussion

The first attempt to understand the mechanism of the chromic acid oxidation of alcohols was made by Westheimer and Novick⁶, who found the rate law for the oxidation of isopropyl alcohol to be :

$$\sqrt{v} = k_a[\text{HCrO}_4^-][\text{R}_2\text{CHOH}][\text{H}^+] + k_b[\text{HCrO}_4^-][\text{R}_2\text{CHOH}][\text{H}^+]^2$$

This rate law has been found to apply to the oxidation of all other primary or secondary alcohols which have been studied⁷.

Table 5. Effect of temperature on the rate of reaction

Temp. (K)	$k \times 10^{-6}$ (s ⁻¹)
313	5.55
318	6.861
323	9.60
328	15.68

Table 6. Thermodynamic parameters

E_a	50.5243 kJ
A	5.0118×10^4
Temperature coefficient	2.0097
ΔH^\ddagger	70.5384 kJ
ΔS^\ddagger	- 88.03 JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
ΔG^\ddagger	98.7842 kJ mol ⁻¹

The most probable reaction sequence was :

Thus only one-third of the total oxidation is effected by chromium(vi) and two-third is effected by chromium(v).

Westheimer then proposed that the oxidation of primary and secondary alcohols proceeded via the acid chromate esters as intermediates.

There were several paths proposed for subsequent

reaction of chromium(IV) thus making possible different mechanism for the oxidation of alcohols. According to Westheimer and Watanabe^{8,9}, subsequent steps must involve chromium(vi).

Scheme 1

The possibilities considered above are feasible when the reaction is carried out homogeneously. But if the oxidant is supported on polymer, which has certain advantages¹⁰ over homogeneous reactions, the mechanism would be preferably according to Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

Chromium(vi) oxidation of alcohols as discussed earlier, proceed through formation of an ester. The ester thus formed will undergo internal oxidation reduction to produce chromium(IV). Since our oxidant was supported on a polymeric material, the intermediate chromium(IV) will further oxidize another molecule of alcohol to a free radical. Thus based on the experimental results obtained for the oxidation of 4-chlorobenzyl alcohol which was found to be zero order, the mechanisms are given in Scheme 3.

Fig. 3. Effect of temperature on the rate of reaction.

The mechanism involves an ester formation as preliminary step¹¹⁻¹⁵.

The ester formed will decompose into aldehyde and the intermediate chromium(IV) will be formed in the second and slow step.

The intermediate chromium(IV) thus formed will further react with another alcohol molecule to produce a free radical. The free radical formation in the reaction was confirmed by the polymerization of added acrylonitrile to the reaction mixture.

Subsequently the free radical will react with another oxidant site in the polymeric reagent to a fast step leading to the formation of chromium(V).

The intermediate chromium(V) in the last step reacts with alcohol to produce aldehyde. The test for formation of chromium(V) and chromium(IV) by their characteristic induced oxidation of iodide⁷ and manganese(II)¹⁶ were not successful probably due to heterogeneity of the reaction mixture.

Scheme 3

Experimental

Preparation of polymer supported chromic acid :
The polymeric reagent (oxidant) was synthesized according to the reported procedure^{10,17,18} starting from Ambersep 900 ($\bar{\text{O}}\text{H}$). The chromate form of 4, 6.5% cross-linked quaternary ammonium resins were prepared following the same procedure.

Determination of capacity of the chromate form of polymeric reagent :

The capacity of the chromate form of polymeric reagent was determined iodometrically (Table 7). The polymer supported chromic acid was used throughout the work. Other chemicals like 1 : 4 dioxane (A.R.), chloroform, CCl_4 , cyclohexane and 4-chlorobenzyl alcohol (Merck) were purified and stored. The strong basic anion exchange resin Ambersep 900 ($\bar{\text{O}}\text{H}$), Acros Organics Company, was used as polymer support.

Table 7. Capacity of chromate form of polymeric reagent

Chromate form of polymeric reagent	Capacity (mmol/g)
6.5% Cross linked	6.50
Ambersep 900 ($\bar{\text{O}}\text{H}$)	6.55
4% Cross linked	6.70

Method of kinetics of oxidation procedure :

The reaction mixture for the kinetic runs was prepared by mixing alcohol, oxidant and solvent. The reaction was carried out with constant stirring using magnetic stirrer and at a constant temperature 45 ± 1 °C. At different time interval, the reaction mixture was withdrawn using a micro-pipette. Care was taken that no solid particles were removed along with the solution. The aliquot thus withdrawn was taken in a stoppered test tube containing $5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3$ of 1 : 4 dioxane and subjected to spectral analysis. The absorbance of the product formed was measured using Shimadzu 160-A UV-Vis spectrophotometer of path length 1 cm and keeping zero time reading as reference. The values reported are the mean of at least two runs and are reproducible within $\pm 3\%$.

Test for free radical :

Initiation of reaction was done by mixing oxidant, 4-chlorobenzyl alcohol and solvent at 318 K with continuous stirring. After 30 min, the reaction mixture was withdrawn in a test tube and acrylonitrile was added. The copious precipitate was formed after dilution of mixture by distilled water. The precipitate formed, due to polymerization of acrylonitrile, indicates formation of a free radical¹⁹ in the reaction.

Product analysis :

The products formed were analyzed by their 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivatives and UV spectra. After completion of reaction (2 h) the resin was filtered off, washed with the solvent and concentrated under reduced pressure to isolate the product. The melting point of the 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivative of benzyl alcohol is 265 °C (λ_{max} 254 nm).

Conclusion :

The linearity of absorbance against time plots and constancy of the zero order rate constants indicate that the reaction neither depends on the polymeric reagent nor the alcohol concentration. This anomalous nature of the reaction may be because the oxidant is taken in the form of a solid supported on polymer. Therefore, the prior equilibria, before the rate determining or the step in which actual reaction takes place giving the product does not seem to contribute to the total rate since they are occurring in different phase i.e. solid phase. This was observed in earlier study of benzoin oxidation by polymer supported *N*-bromo sulphonamide²⁰.

Table 8. Comparison between rates of substituted and unsubstituted benzyl alcohol

Benzyl alcohol (s ⁻¹)	4-Chlorobenzyl alcohol (s ⁻¹)
12.69	6.86

In previous work²¹ we reported the kinetics of oxidation of benzyl alcohol by Cr^{VI} supported on

Ambersep 900 ($\bar{O}H$). In present study due to electron donating effect of Cl⁻ group in 4-chlorobenzyl alcohol the rate of oxidation decreases (Table 8).

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